
AN EFFICIENT APPROACH TO MODEL RESPONSE OF SUBMERGED STRUCTURES TO BLAST LOADING (Paper n. OMAE 96-493)

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ABSTRACT

Blast loading on submerged offshore structures due to fishing activities and hostile attacks is a concern to Oil Operators.

The dynamic response of structures interacting with the fluid has been extensively detailed in the past (e.g. Jackson and Cost, 1980; Jackson and Cost, 1981; Jackson and Jamnia, 1984; Dawson and Sullivan, 1995).

An efficient state-of-the-art methodology is presented to evaluate the structural behavior of underwater nearby blasts to steel and concrete elastoplastic structures. Contact charges require analyses by means of hydrocodes and are not covered in this contribution.

The water shock model and the structure-medium interaction model are treated in detail, while a general description is given for the two dimensional lumped mass incremental implicit beam element code. Due to its nature the code is particularly suited to analyze the response of one dimensional extended structures, but appropriate results have been found also in cases where three-dimensional effects are predominant.

Results of the blast code include time histories of structural ductility, which can be interpreted as a damage indicator in the consequence analyses.

The performance of the blast methodology is evaluated by comparing numerical results with an experimental test of underwater explosion against a stiffened plate.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

A two dimensional lumped mass incremental implicit beam element code (DAPPEXP) that includes non-linear structural behavior, Fluid-Medium Interaction (FMI) and engulfment of the structure by the water shock is presented.

The free-field load histories at every external nodal point on the structure are calculated from explosion effects subroutines and applied to the structure through a FMI model. The subroutine models are constructed from power law fits to the explosion effects database.

The system of equations of structural motion are solved by a central finite difference scheme. The resultant nodal displacements and rotations are used to calculate element end moments, shears, and thrusts that are used to update the system of nodal equations for the next cycle of solution. Output includes: nodal responses (displacement, velocities, and accelerations), element thrusts, shears, moments, ductility and strains, and snapshots of the deformed structure.

A laboratory test is then modeled to present the main features of the beam element code and to evaluate its performance.

2.0 FREE-FIELD PREDICTION

The water shock model is based upon an empirical formula derived over the years from tests and theoretical approximations. For most pressure levels of interest to submerged offshore structures, the pressure field obeys the acoustic laws of wave propagation. Experience (Cole, 1948) has shown that the peak pressure decay with distance from an explosion can be expressed by a basic power law as:

$$P_m = P_o (r/W^{1/3})^v \quad (1)$$

The pressure variation with time $P(r,t)$ can be expressed accurately by:

$$P(r,t) = P_m \exp(-t/t_o) \quad (2)$$

$$t_o = T_o (r/W^{1/3})^\tau \quad (3)$$

The particle velocity $V(r,t)$ in the explosion field obeys the acoustic approximation:

$$V(r,t) = P(r,t) / (\rho_f c) + 1/(\rho_f r) [P(r,t) - P_g] dt \quad (4)$$

where:

- P_m = peak pressure,
- P_o = a pressure constant,
- P_g = hydrostatic pressure,
- T_o = time constant,

- r = radial distance from the explosion center,
 W = explosion charge weight,
 v = attenuation coefficient for pressure,
 τ = coefficient for the time constant,
 ρ_f = density of the water,
 c = velocity of sound in water,
 t = time after the arrival of the shock ($t - r/c$).

The hydrostatic pressure is added to the normal acoustic relationship to limit the growth of the explosion cavity with depth. The constants are provided in the following table for a wide range of different explosive types.

TYPE OF EXPLOSIVE	Po (psi)	To (msec)	v	τ
TNT	21,600	0.052	-1.13	0.23
PENTOLITE	23,500	0.052	-1.14	0.23
H-6	25,800	0.052	-1.19	0.28
HBX-1	22,300	0.056	-1.144	0.247
HBX-2	22,300	0.057	-1.14	0.218

Table 1. Explosive Constants

TNT is chosen as the reference explosive. However, as it can be seen from Table 1, the water shock is not strongly dependent upon the explosive composition. The accuracy of the empirical formulation has been demonstrated by experiment to provide peak pressures and associated time histories within plus minus 10 percent.

3.0 FLUID-MEDIUM INTERACTION MODEL

The explosion effect loading is applied to the beam structural model through the fluid-medium interaction (FMI) model. That is the explosion effects are applied to the finite element nodes through an element that attempts to replace the surrounding medium.

The FMI basis is related to the Taylor plate model. The model is constructed from the interaction of a plane wave in the surrounding fluid interacting with a rigid mass (but moveable) representing the structural reaction. Considering the boundary conditions of continuity of stress and displacement at the interface between the fluid and the structure, the following interface condition results (Crawford et al., 1974):

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_{ff} + \sigma_r = \sigma_{ff} + \rho_f c (V_{ff} - v) \quad (5)$$

where:

- σ_i = interface stress on the structure,
 σ_{ff} = free-field stress caused by the near explosion incident to the structure,
 σ_r = reflected stress from the structure,

- V_{ff} = normal component of free-field particle velocity incident to the structure,
 v = normal component of the structure velocity,
 $\rho_f c$ = acoustic impedance of the fluid defined as the product of the density times the velocity of sound.

This model is the first term of the Doubly Asymptotic Approximation that is widely used by the naval community for evaluation of the explosion response of ships.

The model consequences can be divided into three distinct regimes. In the early time just following the explosion shock impingement on the structure, the velocity of the structure is small, say zero. At that time, the σ_{ff} equals $\rho_f c V_{ff}$, so that the incident normal stress on the structure is nearly doubled, representing the reflected wave from the explosion. However, the incident shock rapidly accelerates the structure with a:

$$a = \sigma_i / m \quad (6)$$

where:

- m = mass of the structural element = $\rho_s L$, where ρ_s is the density of the structure and L is its thickness;

and the structural element quickly approaches exceeding the velocity of the incident particle velocity of the fluid. At that point, the structure (depending upon its resistance) can attain a velocity greater than that of the fluid and the incident stress will fall below the incident explosion produced stress.

Again, depending upon the structure resistance, the interface stress follows the relationship:

$$\sigma_i = 2 \cdot \sigma_{ff} \cdot \exp(-\rho_f c / (m t)) \quad (7)$$

The structure will attain a maximum velocity of about $2 V_{ff}$ very early in time and can quickly outrun the fluid, forming a gap between the fluid and the structure. At this point the structure will continue to deform under the initial kinetic energy imparted by the initial shock wave.

Later in time, the gap between the fluid and the structure will close and the momentum of the fluid particles will again load the structure. However at this time, the maximum interface stress will be controlled by the maximum resistance of the element. Thus the displacement of the fluid and the structure will be about the same later in time.

4.0 PROGRAM LAYOUT

The planar beam elements are loaded with the results of the FMI model in the local coordinate system and are referred to a unit depth of structure. Nodal forces of each element are then transformed to the global coordinate system, and the external node force vector is assembled.

The equations of motion are:

$$M \cdot \ddot{a} + F_I = F_E \quad (8)$$

This may be rewritten as:

$$\bar{a} = \bar{M}^{-1} \cdot (\bar{F}_E - \bar{F}_I)$$

where:

$\bar{M}$ = the mass matrix;

$\bar{M}^{-1}$ = the inverse of the mass matrix;

$\bar{a}$ = X, Y, and θ global accelerations;

$\bar{F}_E$ = the external force vector;

$\bar{F}_I$ = the internal force vector.

The mass matrix is diagonal since a lumped formulation is used. The inverse is simply the reciprocals of each diagonal term. The standard central difference scheme of Equations (9) and (10) for numerical integration can be used to determine displacements and rotations at each time step. By substituting d_j for $x_j - x_{j-1}$ and d_{j+1} for $x_{j+1} - x_j$, we have recast the standard central difference scheme in incremental displacement form as shown in Equations (11) and (12).

$$a_i = \frac{1}{dt^2} \cdot (x_{i-1} - 2 \cdot x_i + x_{i+1}) \quad (9)$$

$$v_i = \frac{1}{2 \cdot dt} \cdot (x_{i+1} - x_{i-1}) \quad (10)$$

where:

a = acceleration (X, Y, or θ component);

v = velocity;

x = displacement;

$i-1$, i , and, $i+1$ subscripts indicate the last, current, and next value.

$$d_{i+1} = a_i \cdot dt^2 + d_i \quad (11)$$

$$v_i = \frac{1}{2 \cdot dt} \cdot (d_i + d_{i+1}) \quad (12)$$

where:

d = incremental displacement;

d_i = $x_i - x_{i-1}$;

d_{i+1} = $x_{i+1} - x_i$;

From the solution of the equations of motion the incremental displacements and total velocities for each node are found. With this information the nodal coordinates and internal forces are updated to prepare for the next solution cycle.

Once the equations of motion have been solved for a particular time step, the internal nodal force vector must be updated for the solution of the next time step. To update the internal force vector the incremental deformations that each element underwent during the time step are used to calculate incremental changes in element axial force, end moments, and end shears. These incremental changes in internal forces are summed with the existing total internal forces to update each element's forces. The internal forces of each element are transformed from local to global coordinates and assembled to form the global internal force vector. The axial force, T , is computed by Equation (13) for each element.

$$T_i = T_{i-1} + \frac{E \cdot A \cdot dl}{l_0} \quad |T_i| \leq T_u \quad (13)$$

where:

T_i = axial force at time = $i \cdot dt$ (the i^{th} time step);

T_{i-1} = axial force from the previous solution cycle;

E = Young's modulus;

A = cross sectional area of the element (thickness since a unit width is used);

dl = incremental change in element length $d_{x2} - d_{x1}$, dl/l_0 is the increment of axial strain;

l_0 = original length of the element;

T_u = ultimate thrust capacity of section.

For the moment calculation, the rigid body rotation of the element must be subtracted from the nodal rotations resulting from the solution of the equations of motion at the previous time step. The incremental moments are based on deformational incremental rotations. The moments for an element are calculated by Equations (14):

$$M1_i = M1_{i-1} + \frac{2 \cdot E \cdot I}{l} \cdot (2 \cdot d\theta_1 + d\theta_2) \quad |M1_i| \leq M_u \quad (14)$$

$$M2_i = M2_{i-1} + \frac{2 \cdot E \cdot I}{l} \cdot (d\theta_1 + 2 \cdot d\theta_2) \quad |M2_i| \leq M_u$$

where:

M_i = moments at nodes 1 and 2 of an element at time = $i \cdot dt$ (the i^{th} time step);

M_{i-1} = moments at nodes 1 and 2 from the previous solution cycle;

I = moment of inertia of the section;

l = current length of the element;

M_u = ultimate moment capacity of section;

$d\theta$ = incremental nodal rotations minus the rigid body rotation of the element, $d\theta_{rb}$;

$$d\theta_{rb} = \frac{dy_2 - dy_1}{1};$$

dy = normal components of incremental displacement at nodes 1 and 2 of the element (local coordinates).

Element shears are calculated as shown in Equation (15):

$$V1_i = \frac{M1_i + M2_i}{1}$$

$$V2_i = -V1_i \quad (15)$$

Damping is treated as an internal force for each element rather than a global term in the numerical integration scheme as in the usual case. This approach provides a means to damp out numerical oscillations associated with the axial response mode and the reverse curvature flexural mode of each element without reducing global responses (rigid body motion). Damping factors are input as a percent of critical damping. Critical damping ratios are defined in Equations (16):

$$C_{cr} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{k \cdot m_e}$$

$$C_{Acr} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{A \cdot E}{1}} \cdot (\rho_e \cdot 1 \cdot A) = 2 \cdot A \cdot \sqrt{E \rho_e}$$

$$C_{Bcr} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{6 \cdot E \cdot I}{1} \cdot \left(2 \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_e \cdot A \cdot 1^3}{24} + \frac{\rho_e \cdot 1 \cdot I}{2} \right) \right)}$$

$$= 4 \cdot \sqrt{3 \cdot E \cdot I \cdot \rho_e \cdot \left(\frac{A \cdot 1^2}{24} + \frac{I}{2} \right)}$$
(16)

where:

- C_{Acr} = critical damping ratio for axial response;
- C_{Bcr} = critical damping ratio for flexural response;
- m_e = mass of element;
- ρ_e = mass density of the element.

The internal damping forces are then calculated as shown in Equations (17):

$$C_x = D \cdot C_{Acr} \cdot \frac{dl}{dt}$$

$$C_\theta = D \cdot C_{Bcr} \cdot \left(\frac{d\theta_1 + d\theta_2}{dt} \right) \quad (17)$$

where:

- C_x = axial damping force;

C_θ = flexural damping force (moment).

Structural capacity demand is simply described by the ductility factor which is the ratio, through time, between the maximum displacement (rotation) and the displacement (rotation) at yielding (Biggs, 1964). For earthquake resistant structures, allowable values of ductility are in the range of 2 - 6, according to safety damage categories. For blast loadings applications ductility levels can reach higher values.

5.0 MODELING OF LABORATORY TEST

The performance of DAPPEXP blast code is presented by numerically simulating an experimental test of explosion in water conducted by the U.S. Navy (Rentz and Shin, 1985).

5.1 Test Setup Description

The test structure was composed of a stiffened plate, geometrically similar to a ship stiffened hull or grillage, and a backing watertight structure to create an air box at the back of the plate. The global structure, detailed in Figures 1a and 1b, was composed of a plate 18 inches by 12 inches and 3/16 inch thick machined from a two inch thick, aluminum blank measuring 33 inches by 27 inches. Two stiffeners (3/16 x 1 inches) were located symmetrically about the centerline. Materials used for the plate and for the backing structure were respectively 6061-T6 aluminum and A36 standard structural steel.

Layout of the test is shown in Figure 2. Eight pound TNT charge weight was fired at nine feet standoff. Large deformations of the plate were achieved with a symmetrical pattern with tearing at the longitudinal edges of the test plate. The greatest deformation at the center measured 1.45 inches. Displacement at different points of the plate have been measured by strain gauges but no pressure time history was provided.

5.2 DAPPEXP Beam Modeling

A 2D beam element code necessarily involves a simple frame pattern. Two rectangular frames (orthogonal) have been modeled to estimate the three dimensional response of the stiffened plate, having smeared the two stiffeners into the model of unit depth by means of an equivalent height of aluminum. The first frame models the structure along the T (transversal) direction (Figure 3a). The following geometrical characteristics are used:

- test plate length: 12 inches;
- backing structure: 27 x 14.5 inches;

The second frame considers the structure along L (longitudinal) direction. Geometrical characteristics are:

- test plate length: 18 inches;
- backing structure: 33 x 14.5 inches;

Modeling details are shown in Figure 3b.

5.3 DAPPEXP Material Modeling

The material model comprises:

- aluminum for test plate;
- steel for backing structure.

Ultimate moment and thrust capacities for the two materials are consistent with the following formulations:

$$M_u = \frac{A h}{4} f_y \quad (18)$$

$$T_u = A f_y \quad (19)$$

where:

- A = area of the element cross section of unitary depth;
- h = height of the section;
- f_y = dynamic yielding stress equal to 47250 psi for aluminum (6061-T6) and 39600 psi for steel (A36).

The moment-thrust interaction is accounted for by means of a simplified rectangular domain. For the current application the general moment-thrust relation is replaced by limiting the actual moment and thrust values at the 70 percent of the ultimate moment and thrust capacities computed for T and M alternatively equal to zero in the moment-thrust diagram, according to Equations (18) and (19), respectively. Material properties of the model are listed in Table 2.

TYPE OF ELEMENT	E (psi)	ρ _e (pcf)	I (in ⁴)	A (in ²)	M _u (in lb)	T _u (in lb)
1 Test Plate	1.02 10 ⁷	168.6	7.5 10 ⁻⁴	0.208	360	6.92 10 ³
2 Back Structure	2.9 10 ⁷	490	2.86	3.25	7.3 10 ⁴	9 10 ⁴

Table 2. Beam Properties

5.4 Results from Numerical Test

Main results from DAPPEXP analyses are shown in Figures 4, 5 and 6. Figure 4 reports relevant time histories of velocities, free-field and interface pressures, and displacements for the two frames.

The test panel is hit by the explosive wave front at 1.8 msec and suddenly moves at a velocity of about 45 m/s. The peak overpressure of the incident wave is about 3800 psi, while pressure resulting from the reflected wave is about 4700 psi.

Maximum vertical displacements reached by the node at the center of the test plate are 0.73 inches for the transversal frame and 1.6 inches for the longitudinal model.

These displacements represent extreme limits to the real measured displacement of the plate of 1.45 inches. In Figure 4e the experimental and the predicted displacement along the longitudinal and transversal axes (L and T) are compared.

In Figure 5 typical structural deformations plots are reported.

Figure 6 shows ductility values at node locations of the test plate. Peak values of ductility are found at the edge between test plate and the backing structure. Tearing along this edge revealed in the experimental test has been numerically verified. In the case of transversal frame, a ductility value of about 19 has been reached; for the longitudinal frame the above value is about 23. The center of the plate enters the plastic field.

6.0 CONCLUSIONS

A simple and efficient elastoplastic finite element approach for modeling the fluid medium interaction response of submerged two dimensional structures to nearby blasts has been presented. An available experimental test of underwater explosion has been used to demonstrate the use of the DAPPEXP beam element code.

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Figure 3a. Transversal Frame Model

Figure 1b. Elevation View of Test Panel

Figure 2. Test Configuration

Figure 1a. Plan View of Test Panel

Figure 3B. Longitudinal Frame Model

Figure 4b. Free-Field Pressure Time History, Node 1

Figure 4a. Velocity Time History, Node 1

Figure 4c. Interface Pressure Time History, Node 1

Figure 4d. Displacement Time History, Node 1

Figure 5. Longitudinal and Transversal Frames, Displacement Plot

Figure 4e. Experimental and Predicted Displacement at long/transv axes

Figure 6. Ductility Demand at Structural Nodes